
Effect of Temperature on the Synthesis of Cathode Salt CuFeO_4 Wet

Abdellatif EL MAGHRAOUI, Abdelaziz ZEROUALE, Mustapha IJJAALI, Ahmed HARRACH

Laboratory of Chemistry of Condensed Mater (LCMC), Sciences and Technology Faculty, Sidi Mohammed Ben Abdellah University. P. O. Box 2202 Fez (Morocco).

Correspondance E-mail: elmaghraabdellatif@yahoo.fr

Abstract Fe (VI) due to the high reduction potential, the large electrochemical capacity and the non-toxic discharge product, are useful for the formation of energetic super-iron batteries of compelling interest. As a result, the synthesis of high-quality cathodic salts proves to be very delicate according to the CuFeO_4 synthesis process which consists in substituting the Barium ions of the ferrate VI obtained by copper, by mixing the BaFeO_4 synthesized with a solution of copper nitrate $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, in order to determine the optimum temperature of the good substitution purity as well as the monitoring of its degradation over time, of which the purity of the reaction is of the order of 99.7% at a temperature of around $[20^\circ\text{C} - 30^\circ\text{C}]$ at $\text{pH} = 11$ for 40 minutes. The phase obtained was characterized by UV spectrophotometer by measuring the optical density at the wavelength 507 nm and analyzed by the volumetric titration method.

Keywords Ferrate, oxidant, electrochemical, cathode, copper ferrate (VI), Purity, Stability

Introduction

Ferrate (VI) is the iron compound with a high oxidation state which has a strong oxidizing power, a relatively high redox potential and an environmentally friendly reduction product. Due to its advantages, ferrate (VI) has been used as an alternative to common oxidants, such as toxic chlorine and chromate, etc. in organic synthesis and wastewater treatment. Recently, "super-iron" batteries have been found to have a higher capacity and energy benefit than conventional alkaline batteries. As summarized in equation (1), ferrate (VI) salts undergo a reduction of three electrons at relatively higher potentials [1–6].

Efficient and economical energy storage is very important for the growing demand of society. Much like fuel cells and lithium-ion batteries, ferrate (VI) materials have also received a lot of attention for their potential used as cathode materials in the development of "super-iron" batteries since the late 1990s due to their energetic, but non-toxic character [7-12].

Currently, there is a need for research and innovation in order to improve the existing preparation methods and to develop new methods which would aim to increase the stability and the yield of the latter.

Scholder et al [13] recommended two methods of synthesizing M_2FeO_4 if M is a divalent element (Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+}) from Fe (III) or from the corresponding alkaline earth metaferrate.

Ferrates (VI) were also prepared from galvanized waste [14], the waste was mixed with ferric oxide in an oven at 800 ° C, the sample was cooled and mixed with sodium peroxide solid then gradually heated for a few minutes. Among the wet and electrochemical methods of synthesis, the dry method avoids the reaction of ferrates with water. This process for preparing ferrates is considered a green technology by recycling various waste iron compounds [15].

In recent years, an increasing number of investigations into the preparation, physico-chemical characterization and detailed performance of certain ferrates (VI). Such as SrFeO₄, BaFeO₄, Na₂FeO₄, Rb₂FeO₄ and Cs₂FeO₄, have appeared in literatures [4, 6, 16, 17]. The solubility of BaFeO₄, a salt more commonly studied in connection with super oxidant iron [18].

Recently, Ag₂FeO₄, with an unusual intrinsic capacity of 5 electrons has also been presented, however, the impurity and instability detract from it as a promising super-iron battery cathode [19]. Attempts to search for alternative ferrate (VI) salts with high intrinsic storage capacity, such as CaFeO₄ and MgFeO₄, etc. will be encouraging.

Calcium ferrate (VI) powders were synthesized from potassium ferrate (VI) and characterized by titration analysis, elemental analyzer, SEM, XRD, IR, TG and DSC. The results showed that the synthesized sample mainly consists of calcium ferrate (VI) and that calcium ferrate (VI) can exist as CaFeO₄ [20].

In 1925, Losana described the preparation of a variety of ferrate salts which included Ba²⁺, Ag⁺, Sr²⁺, Ca²⁺, Pb²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺ and Cu²⁺ by direct precipitation from an aqueous solution of sodium / potassium ferrate with salts of the desired counterion, as well as the preparation of impure salts of Th⁴⁺, Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺ and Al³⁺ [21].

In a similar study, Gump described the preparation of metal salts (Li⁺ -Cs⁺) and La³⁺ ferrates [22].

Material and Method

The synthesis of CuFeO₄ is done by dissolving the ferrate salt of BaFeO₄ prepared in an aqueous solution of copper nitrate Cu(NO₃)₂ at a pH around 11 and temperature of [20°C- 30°C], for 40 minutes in order to obtain a heterogeneous black precipitate which deposits at the bottom of the tube spontaneously and immediately of copper salt, according to the ion exchange reaction (2) of the ferrate VI salt with copper nitrate:

The heterogeneous black precipitate was filtered through filter paper, and washed three times with deionized water. The resulting product CuFeO₄ was dried for 6 h under vacuum at room temperature to give the exact mass of CuFeO₄.

The analysis of the purity of the CuFeO₄ product was determined by arsenite analysis and spectrophotometry.

The material obtained contains less than 0.3% copper equivalent relative to barium as well as arsenite analysis determines that the material is 99.7% pure based on the redox state and the remaining iron is in a lower valence state, although at these relatively low concentration levels, the specific nature of this ferric impurity is difficult to distinguish. It can be assumed that the excess iron exists as several amorphous ferric salts that can be generalized as a 0.3% ferric oxide impurity.

The preparation of BaFeO₄ is done by mixing Ba₃(Fe(OH)₆)₂, H₂O and Ba (OH)₂ pure in a platinum crucible in order to avoid side reactions. The mixture obtained is placed in an oven at a temperature of 850 ° C. under a stream of oxygen for a period of 12 hours with a Ba / Fe ratio = 3, and finally the molten mixture obtained is cooled in a ball dryer [23].

According to the synthesis reaction (3):

The phase found CuFeO₄ was analyzed and followed over time with UV spectrophotometry by measuring the optical density at 507 nm, which is used according to tsapin et al [24], to measure the optical density of the ferrate solution (VI) at a wavelength of 507 nm and pH greater than 10. The characteristic peak of iron (VI) comes out at this wavelength, as well as the volumetric titration method which is based on the reduction of ferrate in ion ferric in solution of excess alkaline arsenite according to reaction (4).

The excess arsenite is then dosed back with bromate according to reaction (5), and thus deduce the equivalent of ferrate.

Results

The yield of the reaction of the synthesis of the CuFeO_4 phase as a function of the pH and the temperature of the reaction medium gives an idea of the progress of the synthesis reaction (Figure 1.2)

Figure 1: Reaction yield of the synthesis of ferrate (VI) CuFeO_4 as a function of the pH of the reaction medium
From the curve (Fig. 1), it is observed that the yield of the ferrate (VI) obtained increases as a function of the pH of the reaction medium up to 99.71% at the value of pH = 11, which implies that the optimum pH of the synthesis reaction medium is around pH = 11. As a result the synthesized compound impurity is almost zero, which makes it more stable and promising for energy storage as cathode materials.

Figure 2: Purity of the ferrate (VI) CuFeO_4 synthesized as a function of the temperature of the reaction medium
According to the curve (Fig. 2), it can be seen that the purity of the ferrate (VI) synthesized decreases with the increase in temperature from [30°C- 40°C], which implies that the optimum temperature of the medium of the synthesis reaction is around [20°C - 30°C], because in this temperature range the purity reaches its maximum.

Evaluation of the stability of synthesized cathodic salt as a function of time

The results of the evaluation of the stability of CuFeO_4 show that the shelf life can reach 12 months with a degradation rate in the first six months is limited to 0.8%.

The results of calculating the rate of degradation between the months and between the state of production and ferrate (VI) and the different months of storage are given in Table 1.

The relation which makes it possible to calculate the percentage of degradation of Iron (VI) is given by the following formula:

$$\% \text{ iron degradation (VI)} = (\text{D.O}_i - \text{D.O}_f) / \text{D.O}_i$$

D.O_i: Optical densities of iron (VI) respectively in the initial state

D.O_f: Optical densities of iron (VI) in the final state

Table 1: Optical density of the CuFeO_4 solution synthesized according to the rate of degradation between the initial state of production and different months of storage of ferrate VI (%) as well as according to the rate of degradation between the months of storage of ferrate VI (%).

t (Months)	The rate of deterioration from baseline in the production and storage of different month ferrate VI (%)	The monthly rate of degradation ferrate VI (%)
1	0.04	0.04
2	0.05	0.01
3	0.06	0.01
4	0.07	0.01
5	0.1	0.03
6	0.8	0.7
7	1.3	0.5
8	1.8	0.5
9	2.3	0.5
10	3.4	1.1
11	3.6	0.2
12	3.9	0.3

According to these results (tab. 1), we notice that the rate of degradation of iron (VI) remains almost invariable as a function of time, recording a small degradation in a different way from one month to another during storage shows the stability of this compound over time.

Discussion

The pH required for the synthesis of iron (VI) stable at room temperature for a yield of 99.7% is of the order of 11 (Figure 1), this is compatible with the results of various preliminary studies [20-21], which show that the adjustment of the pH, the modification of the concentrations of the reagents and the improvement of the procedures of synthesis of ferrate salts like CuFeO_4 by wet way is required.

According to previous studies on the effect of temperature on the purity of the cathodic salt synthesized, it is deduced that the optimum temperature for having pure CuFeO_4 of the order of 99.7% is around [20°C- 30°C], (Fig. 2). Therefore this work is an encouraging progress for the development of industrial processes for the production of ferrates (VI). As this result confirms the studies made by Zhihua Xu and col., 2007 [20], and meant that the decrease in impurities leads to better stability and increases the discharge performance of the copper ferrate sample with a higher intrinsic capacity. Climate change also influences the rate of degradation and the storage time of ferrate (VI) in the room.

Conclusion

This article reviews the effect of temperature on the reaction of synthesis of ferrate (VI) CuFeO_4 pure and stable at room temperature from the reaction of copper nitrate $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and BaFeO_4 whose pH is around of 11, at a temperature of around $[20^\circ\text{C} - 30^\circ\text{C}]$ for a reaction time of the order of 40 minutes.

The process for the wet synthesis of ferrate (VI) of CuFeO_4 from BaFeO_4 is a very easy and very promising method, although there is still a need for further technical, economical improvement regarding industrial application.

References

- [1]. Sharma V. K., *Advances in Environment Research* 6, 143, 2002.
- [2]. Delaude L., Laszlo P., *Journal of Organic Chemistry* 61, 6360, 1996.
- [3]. Licht S., Wang B., Ghosh, S., *Science* 285, 1039, 1999.
- [4]. Licht S., Ghosh S., *Journal of Power Sources* 109, 465, 2002.
- [5]. Walz K.A., Suyam A.N., Suyama W.E., Sene J.J., Zeltner W.A., Armacanqui E.M., Roszkowski A.J., Anderson M.A., *Journal of Power Sources* 134, 318, 2004.
- [6]. Ayers K.E., White N.C., *Journal of the Electrochemical Society* 152, A467, 2005.
- [7]. Wang Z.B., Yin G.P., Shi P.F., "Microwave heated polyol synthesis of carbon-supported PtSn nanoparticles for methanol electrooxidation", *Electrochem. Commun.*, 8(1), 83-90, 2006.
- [8]. Sari A, Kaygusu K., "First and second laws analyses of a closed latciir heat thermal energy storage system", *Chin. J. Chenz. En.*, 12(2), 290-293, 2004.
- [9]. Zhong L., Zhang T.Y., Chen, J.J., Wei G.L., Luo J.L., Chung K., "Effect of H_2S flow rate and concentration on performance of H_2S /air solid oxide fuel cell", *Chin. J. Chem. Eng.*, 12(2), 306-309, 2004.
- [10]. Yu L.J., Yuan J.Q., Cao G.Y., Jiang X.M., "Numerical simulation of dynamic performance of the molten carbonate fuel cell", *Chin. J. Chem. Eng.*, 12(2), 272- 276, 2004.
- [11]. Kim J.W., Ryu J.H., Lee K. T., Oh S. M., "Improve- ment of silicon powder negative electrodes by copper electroless deposition for lithium secondary batteries", *J. Power Sources*, 147(1/2), 227-233, 2005.
- [12]. Tang Z.Y., Feng J.J., Peng Y.N., "Studies on spinel LiMnO , cathode material synthesized from different Mn sources", *Chin. J. Chem. Eng.*, 12(2), 124-127, 2004.
- [13]. Scholder R., Kindervater F., Zeiss W., 1956-b, *Uber orthoferrate IV*, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 283, pp. 330-337, 1956.
- [14]. Cici M., Cuci Y., 1997, production of some coagulant materials from galvanizing workshop waste, *Waste manage.*, 17,7, pp. 407 – 410, 1997.
- [15]. Lee Y.H., M. Cho., Kim J.Y., Yoon J., 2004, Chemistry of ferrate Fe (VI) in aqueous solution and its application as a green chemical, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 10, pp. 161-171, 2004.
- [16]. Licht S., Naschitz, Ghosh V., Lin, S., L., *Electrochemical communication*. 3, 340, 2001.
- [17]. Licht S., Tel-reded R., *Chemical communications* 628, 2004.
- [18]. Licht S., Naschitz V., Wang B., *J. Power sources* 109, 1(67), 2002.
- [19]. Licht S., Yang L., Wang, B., *Electrochemistry Communications*, 7, p. 931, 2005.
- [20]. Zhihua Xu, Jianming Wang, Haibo Shao, Zheng Tang, Jianqing Zhang, Preliminary investigation on the physicochemical properties of calcium ferrate(VI), *Electrochemistry Communications*, 9, pp. 371–377, 2007.
- [21]. Losana L., *Gazz. Chim. Ital*, vol. 55, pages 468-97, 1925.
- [22]. Gump, J., Hart, E., Wagner, W. *Analyt. Chem.* Vol. 24, pages 1497-1498, 1952.
- [23]. El maghraoui A, Zerouale A, Ijjaali M, Synthesis Process of Stable BaFeO_4 by Dry Method, *International Journal of Chemistry and Materials Research*, 3(4): 100-106, 2015. ISSN(e): 2311-763X/ISSN(p): 2312-0991.
- [24]. Tsapin A. I., Goldfeld M. G., Mcdonald G.D., Nealson K.H., Moskovitz B., Solheid p., Klemner W., Kelly S.D., Orlandini K.A., iron (VI): Hypothetical candidate for the Martian Oxidant *Icarus* 147, pp. 68-78, 2000.

